

Research Article

Comparative Assessment of Selected Chemical Properties of Soils in Ivo, Ohaozara and Onicha L.G.As of Ebonyi State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out at Ivo, Ohaozara and Onicha L.G.As. to compare selected chemical properties of soils in those areas. Four replicates of soil samples were collected in each L.G.A. at depths of 0 to 30 cm using soil auger. These soil samples were used for the determination of soil texture, soil pH, organic C, total N, C/N ratio, available P, exchangeable K and cation exchange capacity. Data collected were analysed using standard error and coefficient of variance. Results of the study showed that the soils of the three L.G.As were sandy loam. The pH of soils studied were all strongly acidic, and the order of the increase is Ivo=Ohaozara<Onicha. The lowest organic C value of 1.26% recorded at Onicha was lower than that of Ivo and Ohaozara by 15% and 61% respectively. The order of increase in total N and C/N ratio is Ohaozara >Ivo>Onicha. Onicha recorded the highest available phosphorus value of 16.65mgkg⁻¹ whereas the lowest available P value of 13.58mgkg⁻¹ was observed at Ivo. Apart from Onicha which recorded 0.31 Cmol(+)⁻¹kg⁻¹ value of exchangeable K, the values of exchangeable K observed in the other two L.G.As. were below 0.20 Cmol(+)⁻¹kg⁻¹ regarded as the critical limit of exchangeable K in soils. The highest CEC value of 7.90 Cmol(+)⁻¹kg⁻¹ recorded in Onicha was higher than that of Ivo and Ohaozara by 29% and 17% respectively. These soils were strongly acidic and low in plant nutrient, therefore, the application of lime, organic and inorganic fertilizers is indispensable for optimum crop performance in them.

INTRODUCTION

Soil nutrient depletion, as a result of continuous cultivation of soils without adequate addition of external inputs, is a major challenge to farmers in Ivo, Ohaozara and Onicha L.G.As. of Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Similarly, many tropical soils have low organic matter and as a result, some physiochemical characteristics of such soils are not at optimum levels for high and sustained productivity (Mbagwu, 1989; Mbah *et al.*, 2011). Thus, farmers in Ivo, Ohaozara and Onicha L.G.As. face the problems of maintaining soil productivity. According to Mbah and Mbagwu (2006), and Njoku and Mbah (2012), soil infertility is a major over-riding constraint that affect all aspects of crop production.

Haynes and Naidu (1998) observed that at low pH, acid soils are normally flocculated and that as pH is raised by addition of organic wastes, the net negative charge on soil surfaces is increased and the ratio of negative to positive charges also increases. At the same time, Al^{3+} activity declines as Al precipitates to hydroxyl-Al polymers and as a result, repulsive forces between particles dominate and lead to soil dispersion. Organic matter plays a major role in soil physical, chemical and biological properties and acts as a source of nutrients, while increase nutrients exchange sites and affect the fate of applied pesticides (Alabandan *et al.*, 2009).

Soils in Ebonyi State have been reported to have several problems such as low bulk density, extreme consistency conditions, compaction and poor drainage (Nnabude and Mbagwu, 2001; Okonkwo *et al.*, 2012). Similarly, Mbagwu and Piccolo (1990) reported low pH, shallow depth, and low cation exchange capacity as other common constraints to crop production in the area. The use of organic and inorganic fertilizer cannot be avoided in intensive agriculture for good crop yields, and knowledge of the soil is important for proper management of soils of these areas. Therefore, the objective of this study is to compare selected chemical properties of soils in Ivo, Ohaozara and Onicha L.G.As. of Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Ivo, Ohaozara and Onicha Local Government Areas made up the defunct Ohaozara Local Government Area, which was created from the defunct Afikpo Division in 1976. These Local Government Areas lie at the southwest of Ebonyi State, Nigeria. They have mean annual rainfall of 1700 – 1800 mm. The rainfall pattern of the area is bimodal between April – July and September – November with short spell in August. According to Ofomata (1975), the minimum and maximum temperatures of the area are 27°C and 31°C respectively. The relative humidity of the area is between 60

and 80 %. The soil belongs to the order Ultisol and is classified as Typic Haplustult (Federal Department of Agriculture and Land Resources, 1985).

Soil Sampling and Laboratory Analysis

Soil samples were collected in four replicates at each L.G.A. at depths of 0 to 30 cm using soil auger in January 2010. Each sample was immediately placed in a labeled plastic bag and tightly sealed. All the samples were transported to the laboratory where on arrival, analytical procedure commenced immediately. Soil texture was determined from initial soil sample, using the Bouyoucous hydrometer method as described by Gee and Bauder (1986). The pH of the soil was determined using a suspension of 2g soil and 5ml of distilled water (McLean, 1982). Total nitrogen was determined using modified Kjeldahl digestion procedure (Bremner and Mulvaney, 1982). Organic carbon was determined by the method of Nelson and Sommers (1982). Available phosphorus was determined by Bray 11 method (Olsen and Sommers, 1982). Cation exchange capacity and exchangeable potassium was determined using Chapman (1982) method.

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis of the data was carried out using standard error and coefficient of variance (Steel and Torrie, 1980).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Selected chemical properties of the soils

Selected chemical properties of the soils in Ivo, Ohaozara and Onicha L.G.As. of Ebonyi State, Nigeria, are presented in the table 1. The results of the study showed that the soils of the three local government areas (L.G.As) studied are sandy loam. According to Anikwe and Nwobodo (2002), sandy loamy soil is usually highly permeable and allows large quantities of leachates to pass through it. As a result of this high permeability, soils of this texture contain poor plant nutrients, and therefore, organic or inorganic fertilizer is needed to improve their productivity levels.

The pH of the soils studied were all strongly acidic, and the order of increase is Ivo=Ohaozara<Onicha. The strongly acidic nature of the soils of the L.G.As. could be attributed to high cropping intensity (which result to the assimilation of most of the basic cations by the crops) and moderate rainfall (which causes leaching). For these soils to increase their productivity, liming is needed.

The lowest organic C value of 1.26% recorded at Onicha was lower than that of Ivo and Ohaozara by 15% and 61%, respectively; and according to the Federal Department of Agriculture and Land Resources (1990),

Table 1: Selected chemical properties of soils in Ivo, Ohaozara and Onicha L.G.As., Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

L.G.A.	Soil Texture	Soil pH	Organic C (%)	Total N (%)	C/N Ratio	Avail P (MgKg ⁻¹)	Exchangeable K (Cmol(+) ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹)	CEC (Cmol(+) ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹)
Ivo	Sandy loam	4.95±0.05	1.45±0.01	0.17±0.01	8.52±0.17	13.78±0.12	0.17±0.01	5.60±0.07
Ohaozara	Sandy loam	4.95±0.16	2.03±0.06	0.21±0.02	9.67±0.21	13.58±0.19	0.13±0.01	6.57±0.17
Onicha	Sandy loam	5.17±0.11	1.26±0.04	0.15±0.01	8.40±0.13	16.65±0.23	0.31±0.02	7.90±0.12
CV (%)		3	25	21	8	12	47	17

Organic C at Ivo and Onicha are low while that of Ohaozara is medium. These could be as a result of low natural organic matter returns and other human factors such as crop removal and bush burning. Hence, the application of organic fertilizer is needed for some physiochemical characteristics of such soils to be at optimum levels for high and sustained productivity (Mbagwu, 1989; Mbah *et al.*, 2011).

The values of total N observed in Ivo, Ohaozara and Onicha are 0.17%, 0.21% and 0.15%, respectively. These nitrogen content reflect organic carbon content of phosphorus with aluminum and iron to form complex compound such as aluminum phosphate (Al₃PO₄) and iron phosphate (FePO₄), which are fixed in the soil and not readily available for plants. The fixed phosphorus can be made to be readily available with the application of organic amendments. Njoku and Mbah (2012) and Mbah and Onweremadu (2009) observed that application of organic amendments make phosphorus to be more available in the soils.

The values of exchangeable K obtained in Ivo, Ohaozara and Onicha were 0.17, 0.13 and 0.31 Cmol(+)⁻¹kg⁻¹, respectively. This exchangeable K in all the three areas were low, with those of Ivo and Ohaozara below 0.20 Cmol(+)⁻¹kg⁻¹ regarded as the critical limit of exchangeable K in soils (Onyekwere *et al.*, 2001). The highest CEC value of 7.90 Cmol(+)⁻¹kg⁻¹ was recorded in Onicha. The observed CEC in Onicha was higher than that of Ivo and Ohaozara by 29% and 17%, respectively. Again, these observed CEC were so low that these soils would require either organic or inorganic fertilizer to increase their productive capacity.

CONCLUSION

Federal Department of Agriculture and Land Resources (1985). Reconnaissance soil survey of Anambra State Nigeria; Soil Report FDALR, Kaduna.
Federal Department of Agriculture and Land Resources (1990). Soil survey of Nigeria and rating for soil data

the soils (Onyekwere *et al.*, 2003). The order of increase in C/N ratio is Ohaozara>Ivo>Onicha.

Onicha recorded the highest available phosphorus value of 16.65mgkg⁻¹. This observed available phosphorus at Onicha was higher than that of Ivo and Ohaozara by 21% and 18%, respectively. The soil pH might have influenced the level of availability of phosphorus since the availability of phosphorus and its solubility is pH dependent. Ozubor and Anoliefo (1999) observed that soils with low pH value result in the reaction of This study has shown that soils of Ivo, Ohaozara and Onicha L.G.As are sandy loam, strongly acidic and poor in plant nutrients. For these soils to provide good crop yields, organic fertilizer must be used in tandem with inorganic fertilizer. Also, to reduce the acidity of soils in the three L.G.As., they must be limed occasionally.

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